

Exercises in Archaeoastronomy - 2 - The passage mound of Newgrange

Amelia Carolina Sparavigna

Department of Applied Science and Technology, Politecnico di Torino

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Abstract

Here it is given the second article of a series proposing exercises in archaeoastronomy. The reader can find exercises about the apparent motion of the sun, and its azimuth and altitude given in the horizontal coordinate system. As case study, we investigate the orientation of the prehistoric passage mound of Newgrange.

In the previous article [1], we have introduced a series of exercises in archaeoastronomy. Let us start the series by studying the sun and its horizontal coordinates. After exercises on azimuth and altitude of the sun, we consider some prehistoric monuments. In particular we propose exercises on the passage mound of Newgrange, as a case study.

First, some definitions. Let us consider the horizon. In astronomy, and therefore in archaeoastronomy, we have to distinguish two horizons. One is the astronomical horizon, which is the horizon that would be seen if the earth's surface were perfectly smooth. It is given by the intersection with the celestial sphere of the local horizontal plane, passing through the observer. The second horizon is the natural or sensible horizon, that is, the line at which the sky and Earth appear to meet. If we use a software simulating azimuth and altitude of the sun or of the moon, such as Sollumis.com, SunCalc.net, SunCalc.org, MoonCalc.org, we have to remember that the lines representing azimuths are given on an astronomical horizon. Therefore, it is possible that, locally, the sunrise is not visible with that specific azimuth, due to the presence of hills and mountains. The same for the visibility of the stars; it is depending on the local natural horizon. As a consequence, when we are considering the astronomical orientations of architectural complexes by means of the above mentioned software, we have to remember that we are doing a preliminary analysis, which is using the local astronomical horizon. This approach allows to evidence the possible existence of alignments along the rise or setting of celestial bodies. After this study, we can make a further analysis by means of the local natural horizon. For this next analysis, we can use Google Earth, and its tool giving the elevation profile (or its tool giving the sun in the local natural horizon [1]). Of course, if possible, a direct survey of the site will be the final goal of our work.

Before continuing, let us observe the following. We could have an ideal orientation or a natural orientation of the considered site. In the first case, the orientation could be just symbolic, not referring to the actual point of the natural horizon where the sun, the moon or some stars are rising, because the orientation is imagined in an ideal horizon. In the second case, it is prevailing

the natural point of the horizon where the celestial object is rising or setting. And probably this point is related to a landmark, such as a peak or a hill, of the local landscape. Therefore, we have always to consider if the horizon had been symbolic or natural for the people that built the monument.

Being the horizon an object which is a little bit more complex of what we have previously told, I suggest to read the site en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Horizon, which is also explaining the role of the Earth's curvature and atmosphere in the appearance of the celestial objects. For sunrise and sunset, see also [wiki/Sunrise](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Sunrise) and [wiki/Sunset](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Sunset).

In one of the software that we will use for the exercises (suncal.org, remarkable software by Torsten Hoffman www.torsten-hoffmann.de) we find azimuth and altitude of the sun for any time of the day, for any day of the year. Azimuth and altitude are the coordinates of an object in the horizontal frame of reference. This coordinate system uses the observer's local astronomical horizon as the fundamental plane. The altitude is also known as elevation or height. In the Figure 1, we can see the altitude angle and azimuth (please read also [wiki/Horizontal_coordinate_system](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Horizontal_coordinate_system)).

Figure 1: Horizontal frame of reference (adapted from an image by Joshua Cesa).

Let us note that the sunrise azimuth changes on any day of the year. Therefore, the sun is rising on the East only at the equinoxes. And in fact, in the Cambridge Dictionary, we find that "east" is defined as "the direction where the sun rises in the morning that is opposite west" [2], and this happens at equinoxes. From now on, let us remember that we will use the terms East and West (North and South) only for the points of the compass.

First, let us start from sunrise and sunset azimuths, using software sollumis.com. The site tells that the software is giving "The time and direction of sunset, noon, and sunrise for any location". We can click on the map or search any location. "The lines on the drawing show the direction and height (altitude) of the sun throughout the day. Thicker and shorter lines mean the sun is higher in the sky. Longer and thinner lines mean the sun is closer to the horizon." In a panel on the left (Figure 2), we can read sunrise and sunset azimuths and the noon altitude. Noon altitude is the meridian altitude, used for navigation to calculate an observer's latitude. The meridian altitude is

the altitude of the sun (or of another object) when it passes the observer's meridian. Read more at [wiki/Meridian_altitude](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Meridian_altitude).

Sollumis.com is one of the first software that used Google images, showing on them the direction of the sun. Moreover, Sollumis.com was the first software I used for investigations concerning archaeoastronomy [3-6]. As told in [1], another software, which is giving the direction of sunrise and sunset on satellite images is suncalc.net. This software was first used for archaeoastronomy in [7], for the analysis of the site of Lepenski Vir.

Exercise 1: Using sollumis.com, find your home and determine for some days of the year, the sunrise and sunset azimuths. For the day when you are doing the exercise, compare the results given by software to the direct observation of the natural horizon. Solution: you can read sunrise and sunset azimuth in the left panel of the software (see Figure 2).

Exercise 2: Using the same software, determine the altitude of the sun when it is passing your meridian. Solution: Again, you can read information in the left panel of software. For instance, on February 12, Torino, the meridian altitude is 31 degrees. Let us note the azimuth in sollumis.com is rounded to the nearest degree.

Figure 2: Thanks to sollumis.com, we can have sunrise and sunset azimuths and the noon altitude.

Exercise 3: Using suncalc.org, determine the altitude of the sun when it is passing your meridian. Solution: Use the cursor at the top of the web page. You can read information in the left panel of software. For instance, on February 12, in Torino, the meridian altitude is 31.34 degrees (Figure 3). In the software, you can see the points of the compass too. The meridian is the N-S dashed line.

Figure 3: Thanks to suncalc.org, we can have more information concerning the sun.

Exercise 4: Using suncalc.org, determine the meridian altitude of the sun on December 21 for the following sites: Newgrange, Paris, Rome, Singapore, Yogyakarta, Canberra and Quito. Save the data and compare results. Solution: Repeat the method of Exercise 3 for the given sites. Let us note that software suncalc.org, like software suncalc.net, is giving a yellow shadowed area, which is comprised between the apparent motion of the sun on December 21 and June 21. The following Figure 4 shows images obtained by means of screenshots of suncalc.net for Paris, Quito and Canberra. Observe the images carefully. Why they are so different?

Figure 4: Screenshots from suncalc.net.

Exercise 5: In en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Newgrange, we read that the site of Newgrange "consists of a large circular mound with an inner stone passageway and chambers. ... Its entrance is aligned with

the rising sun on the winter solstice, when sunlight shines through a 'roofbox' and floods the inner chamber". Find the sunrise azimuth at Newgrange on December 21. Solution: First, let us consider Newgrange and use sollumis.com. We read a sunrise azimuth of 131 degrees. Then, let us use suncalc.org. To read the sunset azimuth, we have to move the cursor slowly. We have: azimuth 131.29 degrees, altitude 0.06 degrees. See also Figure 5. Read again en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Sunrise.

Figure 5: Newgrange seen in SunCalc.org. Note that the pivot is positioned so that the line of the sunrise in passing through the entrance (azimuth 131.69 and altitude 0.25 degrees). Of course, we cannot see the passageway inside, and therefore we can only conclude a possible alignment. As told in [8,9], "As early as 1909, Lockyer remarked that the passage grave was approximately aligned to the rising Sun at midwinter. He did not, however, pay much attention to the site." Let us remember the book [10] by Lockyer.

Exercise 6: Consider the sites of Maeshowe in Orkney, Scotland, and Bryn Celli Ddu in Wales, how are their entrances aligned? Solution: use suncalc.net and visit the sites. You can see also [11] for instance. For pictures and maps, search Bryn Celli Ddu and the other site by www.megalithic.co.uk/search.php.

When the above mentioned suncalc.org/.net are used, be careful if you move towards the Arctic Circle. Consider the simulations only after a careful check of the results. The Arctic Circle marks the northernmost point at which the noon sun is just visible on the December solstice. The Circle marks also the southernmost point at which the midnight sun is just visible on the June solstice. Above the circle, we have the Arctic: as seen from this zone of the Earth, the Sun is above the horizon for 24 continuous hours at least once per year and below the horizon for 24 continuous hours at least once per year (and therefore not visible at noon). This is also true in the Antarctic region, south of

the Antarctic Circle. Let us note that the position of the Arctic Circle is not fixed, because its latitude depends on the Earth's axial tilt, which fluctuates within a margin of 2 degrees over a 40,000-year period [12]. "By definition, - wiki/Circle_of_latitude explains - the positions of the Tropic of Cancer, Tropic of Capricorn, Arctic Circle and Antarctic Circle all depend on the tilt of the Earth's axis relative to the plane of its orbit around the sun (the "obliquity of the ecliptic"). If the Earth were "upright" (its axis at right angles to the orbital plane) there would be no Arctic, Antarctic, or Tropical circles: at the poles the sun would always circle along the horizon, and at the equator the sun would always rise due east, pass directly overhead, and set due west".

Exercise 7. Consider the Figure 6, and imagine the motion of the sun in the four proposed cases.

Figure 6: The motion of the sun as seen by an observer at the centre of the sphere, for the given latitudes.

So we have seen in the satellite images the passage mound of Newgrange (wiki/Newgrange). Newgrange, or Brú na Bóinne, was built during the Neolithic period, around 3200 BC, "making it older than Stonehenge and the Egyptian pyramids" as told by Wikipedia. The site is a large circular mound (diameter of 76 metres), having an inner stone passageway and chambers. It is not only a passage tomb in a mound, it is a monument where the mound possesses a retaining wall with a monumental entrance made by decorated stones.

Wikipedia tells that "There is no agreement about what the site was used for, but it is believed that it had religious significance". Of the link to the winter solstice we have already told in Exercise 5, and of the 'roofbox', through which the light of the sun is flooding the inner chamber during the sunrise on that day (more details at [8,9]). Wikipedia notes that "Several other passage tombs in Ireland are aligned with solstices and equinoxes, and Cairn G at Carrowkeel has a similar 'roofbox'. Newgrange also shares many similarities with other Neolithic constructions in Western Europe, such as Maeshowe in Orkney, Scotland, and Bryn Celli Ddu in Wales".

Wikipedia continues "Many archaeologists believed that the monument [Newgrange] had religious significance of some sort", linked to a "cult of the dead" or to an "astronomically-based faith. The archaeologist Michael J. O'Kelly, who led the 1962–1975 excavations at the site, ... believed that Newgrange, alongside the hundreds of other passage tombs built in Ireland during the Neolithic, showed evidence for a religion which venerated the dead as one of its core principles. He believed that this "cult of the dead" was just one particular form of European Neolithic religion, and that

other megalithic monuments displayed evidence for different religious beliefs which were solar, rather than death-oriented" (Wikipedia and [13]). In fact, other scholars have offered an alternative interpretations, in which Newgrange was a monument designed for the capture of the sun on the Winter Solstice. "Once a year, the rising sun of the solstice shines along the long passage of the mound, illuminating the inner chamber. ... Michael J. O'Kelly was the first person in modern times to observe this event on 21 December 1967" (Wikipedia). O'Kelly was the person that led the most extensive excavation of the site and also reconstructed the frontage of the mound. Actually, as Wikipedia explains, "after its initial use, Newgrange was sealed for several millennia". However, it persisted in the Irish mythology and folklore, as a dwelling place of the gods Dagda and his son Aengus. The first antiquarian studies began during the 17th century, and some excavations took place in the years that followed.

As explained in [14], over the course of the excavation, "some of the many local visitors would often tell the O'Kelly's of a tradition, that the rising sun, at some unspecified time, would light up the triple spiral stone in the end recess of the chamber at Newgrange. Unfortunately, no one could be found who had witnessed this but it continued to be mentioned, ... A conversation between the O'Kellys (Michael J. and his wife Claire) on the persistence of this tradition, planted in the mind of the Professor that," an orientation of the passageway towards the winter solstice was possible and that the local tradition was based on a real fact. Therefore, O'Kelly decided to reach Newgrange on the day before the winter solstice. "Some minutes before sunrise on the 21st of December 1967", O'Kelly was alone in the darkness of the inner chamber of the mound, waiting and considering if anything would happen. "To his amazement, minute by minute, the chamber grew steadily lighter and a beam of sunlight began to enter the passage and to travel inwards, 'lighting up everything as it came until the whole chamber – side recesses, floor and roof six metres above the floor – were all clearly illuminated'. O'Kelly stood rigid for a while, transfixed by the phenomenon and convinced and fearful in his own imagination that the Dagda, the sun god, who according to the ancient tradition had built the tomb, was about to hurl the roof upon him" [14,15].

The spectacular phenomenon observed by O'Kelly is slightly different from the original one. "When Newgrange was built over 5000 years ago, the winter solstice sunbeam would have made its way to the back recess of the central chamber. Due to changes in the tilt of the Earth's axis the sunbeam now stops 2 metres from the back recess" (www.knowth.com/winter-solstice.htm). And also, "At dawn, on solstice after 9 am the Sun begin to rise across the Boyne Valley from Newgrange over a hill known as Red Mountain. For the following seventeen minutes, between 19 and 23 December, the sunbeam stretches into the narrow passage of Newgrange tomb and on into the central chamber. In Neolithic times it illuminated the rear stone of the central recess of the chamber" [16].

So, let us investigate the local elevation profile.

Exercise 8. Using Google Earth, determine the elevation profile along the sunrise azimuth on solstice, in front of the Newgrange monument. Solution: It is given in the Figure 7.

Figure 7: Thanks to Google Earth, we can use a straight edge to draw the red line in the image. The software is giving the corresponding elevation profile (support.google.com/earth/answer/148134?hl=en). The image in the Figure is obtained by two screenshots. The elevation of Newgrange (top of the mound) is 64 m, that of the nearest hill 93 meters, at a distance of 2700 meters. Since the mound is 12 meters high, the entrance has an elevation of 52 meters. The radius of the mound is of about 38 meters. To see half of the sun, it is necessary that the centre of the mound is of about 38 meters. To see half of the sun has an altitude of about a degree (calculus: $\arctan ((93-52) / 2662) = 0,88$ degree). Let us note that the sun has an angular diameter of 0.5 degrees.

Here, let us consider this value of 1 degree as the value of the altitude of the sun, to have its rays reaching the place in the inner chamber where there is the stone basin, shown in [17]. If we consider the figure in this reference, we can prepare a plan of the passage as we are giving in the Figure 8. Let us suppose to consider the winter solstice of 2017, and imagine the sun when it has the same azimuth as it had at the time when Newgrange was built. Today, we know that the rays of the sun stop two meters before the back recess (and therefore let us imagine they stop two meters before the basin). It means that the sun (today) is about 0.7 degrees higher, than it was in origin. This happens because of a very slow change of the tilt of the Earth's axis. Considering a difference of 0.7 degrees, we can estimate the following: when Newgrange was built the sunrise azimuth on winter solstice was larger of an angle comprised between 1.0 and 1.5 degrees (we will discuss in more detail the role of the tilt of the Earth's axis in a future article, during a discussion of the Karnak temple in Egypt).

Figure 8: This image is showing a sketch of the passage inside Newgrange. The figure gives two rays passing through the roofbox, one imagined today (1.7 degrees), the other at the time when Newgrange was built (1.0 degrees). The difference is due to the very slowly change of the Earth's axis.

Let us do a last simulation, using CalSky (CalSky: #1 Astronomical and Space Calendar, <https://www.calsky.com/>, The most complete astronomical observation and information online-calculator on this globe: make your own calendar with satellites, asteroids, comets, planets, sun, and moon). Select Sun, the Rise and Set. To setup the location, use the globe on the right of the page and search Newgrange. After select date and period. For instance, 21 December 2018. The result is given in the Table I. In the web page, we find a glossary too. "Rise and set times are for a mathematical horizon, corrected for standard refraction ... ". Read the glossary carefully.

additionally, list times of civil (-6°) and astronomical (-18°) twilight

21 Dec 2018	Rise : 8h41.0m az=130.7°	Set : 16h06.9m az=229.3°	Transit: 12h23m58s Altitude=12.9° Sgr
	Dawn : 7h12m	Dusk : 17h36m	Day : 7h25.9m

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Table I

From the Table, we have that the sunrise azimuth is 130.7 degrees (time 8h 41.0m) and the sunset azimuth is 229.3 degrees (time 16h 06.9m). Altitude is 12.9° in Sgr. Day: 7h 25.9m long. If we use a date of 3200 BC, we see that no results are given for sunrise. We see results given from 1500 BC. The Table II shows them. The southernmost sunrise is at azimuth 131.6 degrees (time 8h 28.6m) and the sunset azimuth is 228.4 degrees (15 h 47.7 m). Altitude 12.5° in Cap. Day: 7h 19.1m long.

1 Jan 1499BC	Rise : 8h28.0m az=131.6°	Set : 15h47.2m az=228.4°	Transit: 12h07m38s Altitude=12.5° Cap
	Dawn : 6h58m	Dusk : 17h17m	Day : 7h19.2m
2 Jan 1499BC	Rise : 8h28.6m az=131.6°	Set : 15h47.7m az=228.4°	Transit: 12h08m07s Altitude=12.5° Cap
	Dawn : 6h58m	Dusk : 17h18m	Day : 7h19.1m
3 Jan 1499BC	Rise : 8h29.0m az=131.6°	Set : 15h48.2m az=228.4°	Transit: 12h08m35s Altitude=12.5° Cap
	Dawn : 6h59m	Dusk : 17h18m	Day : 7h19.2m
4 Jan 1499BC	Rise : 8h29.4m az=131.6°	Set : 15h48.8m az=228.5°	Transit: 12h09m04s Altitude=12.5° Cap
	Dawn : 6h59m	Dusk : 17h19m	Day : 7h19.4m

Table II

From these results we could extrapolate that the sunrise azimuth, at the time Newgrange was built, was of about 132 degrees and the noon altitude of 12.3 degrees.

Let us conclude stressing that Newgrange is a remarkable monument. Moreover, as told in [8,9], "Newgrange predates the astronomical structures of Stonehenge by 1,000 years and as such may be the oldest astronomically orientated structure in the world". Other references about Newgrange are given in [18-20]. Links showing images and pictures of Newgrange can be find at: www.newgrange.com/newgrange-plans.htm, www.newgrange.com/winter-solstice-09.htm, www.ancient-wisdom.com/lightboxes.htm.

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